

PMK1, an improved rainfed lowland rice variety for Tamil Nadu, India

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PMK1 (Co 25/ADT31), a high-yielding, and widely adapted rainfed lowland rice variety, matures in 115-120 d. It has long, compact panicles with golden yellow grains, white rice, and good cooking quality.

The early seedling vigor exhibited by

Performance of PMK1 in research station and adaptive research trials. Tamil Nadu, India, 1980-83.

Year	Yield (t/ha)		Increase (%) over TKM9
	PMK1	TKM9	
1980	3.4	2.8	21.9
1981	3.0	2.2	36.1
1982	3.0	2.5	18.1
1983	2.2	1.9	19.7
Mean ^a	2.9	2.3	23.9
1983 ^b	3.1	2.7	12.1

^aResearch station trials. ^bAdaptive research trials, 20 sites.

PMK1 helps it compete with weeds at the early vegetative phase.

In yield trials for 4 yr in Aug-Dec season, average grain yield were 2.9 t/ha, 23.9% more than TKM9, a high-yielding, semidwarf, rainfed lowland rice (see table). In the Adaptive Research Trials of 1983-84, PMK1 produced an average grain yield of 3.06 t/ha, 12.1% more than TKM9. It is a good straw yielder as well.

PMK1 is 110 cm high, photoperiod insensitive, and lodging resistant. It matures in 120 d. A thousand grains weigh 24 g and cooking quality 15 good.

PMK1 is tolerant of blast and bacterial leaf blight in the field. *☞*

NC492 (IET8970), a promising variety for rainfed lowlands in West Bengal

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NC492, a pureline selection from Boyan (Acc. 30250), was identified at Chinsurah after it survived submergence for 3 d in late Sep 1978, when a record 523.9 mm of rain fell at RRS 15 d after planting. In station trials and adaptive trials at 6 sites from 1979 to 1982, NC492 yielded an average 4.7 t/ha, compared to 3.4 t/ha for Mahsuri.

NC492 was nominated for the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) semideep water trial (Uniform Variety Trial 5 [UVT 5]) and tested at 7 sites during 1982 kharif. It ranked first (3.8 t/ha) in overall mean yield (Table 1).

In tests at 11 sites in 1983, NC492 ranked second, with a marginal yield difference of only 45 kg/ha less than the first ranking variety CN505-5-32-9 (IET8967). In 1984, NC492 yielded an average 2.9 t/ha at 8 sites. It ranked first in the Physiology Screening Trial for waterlogged conditions (AICRIP) conducted with UVT 5 entries in 1982 and 1983 (Table 2).

NC492 is photoperiod sensitive, lowering in late October. It is semitall

Table 1. Performance of NC492 in 1982-83 national trials (UVT 5). West Bengal, India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)				Maximum water depth (cm)	
	NC492		Tillakkachari		1982	1983
	1982	1983	1982	1983		
Pulla	3.2	2.4	1.8	1.6	70	75
Patna	3.2	2.6	2.8	2.0	—	31
Pusa	2.7	1.4	2.1	0.8	70	60
Sindri	1.3	3.7	1.3	2.9	50	36
Bhubaneswar	4.6	—	2.3	—	—	—
Chinsurah	6.2	3.1	4.3	1.6	40	50
Cuttack Rice Research Institute	—	3.6	—	2.7	—	41
Ranital	—	4.6	—	2.4	—	—
Sabour	—	1.0	—	1.1	—	63
Arundhutinagar	5.1	—	4.1	—	—	—
Mean	3.8	2.8	2.6	1.8	—	—

Table 2. Performance of NC492 in 1982-83 Physiology Screening Trials for waterlogged conditions (AICRIP).

Site	Yield (t/ha)					
	NC492		Tillakkachari		Other check	
	1982	1983	1982	1983	1982	1983
Baruipur	4.5	4.5	3.9	3.8	2.9	1.0
Chinsurah	4.9	5.3	3.1	4.7	(Mahsuri) 4.3	(Pankaj) 4.2
Cuttack	3.4	4.7	3.2	3.7	(NC488) 3.1	(NC487) 3.1
Patna	4.2	3.2	4.6	4.0	(Mahsuri) 2.6	(Mahsuri) 2.1
Mean	4.2	4.5	3.7	4.0	(Pankaj) 3.2	(BR34) 2.6

(about 150 cm) with moderate culm stiffness and good seedling vigor. The panicle is about 26 cm long with 160-170

golden color grains.

The variety has a shape index of 3.75, 1,000-grain weight of 32 g, and strong

dormancy of about 12 wk. It is moderately resistant to sheath blight, brown spot, and stem borer.

The 1984 Annual Rice Workshop

(AICRIP) recommended NC492 as a promising variety for semideep water situations in West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, and Andhra Pradesh. It has been

recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers fields for 2 yr and is in the prerelease stage in West Bengal. *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Character association in upland rice cultivars of India

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Ninety-eight local ricecultivars grown in a randomized block design with three replications in July 1983 were assessed

for the association among 11 traits at the genotypic (r_g) and phenotypic (r_p) levels (see table).

In general, genotypic associations were higher than phenotypic, but values of both were either positive or negative. This indicates that r_p is slightly reduced by environmental effects. At both the r_g and r_p levels, yield per plant was positive and significantly associated with days to flowering, leaf angle, leaf length, plant height, panicle length, sheath length,

tillers per plant, and grains per panicle. Yield per plant was associated with test weight only at the r_g level. Tillers per plant and test weight directly contributed to yield. Other auxiliary traits that showed positive association with yield were also positively associated among themselves. Any one of these traits could be utilized as selection criteria for yield improvement in upland rice. *S*

Genotypic (G) and phenotypic (P) associations among 11 traits of upland rices. ^a

Trait		Culm angle	Leaf angle	Leaf length	Plant height	Panicle length	Sheath length	Tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	Test weight	Grain yield/plant
Days to flowering	G	-0.08	0.45**	0.52**	0.53**	0.58**	0.40**	0.05	0.49**	-0.06	0.31**
	P	-0.08	0.41**	0.37**	0.50**	0.48**	0.26**	0.03	0.41**	-0.07	0.20*
Culm angle	G		0.17	0.14	-0.21*	-0.25**	0.11	-0.10	-0.13	0.20*	-0.08
	P		0.17	0.08	-0.17	-0.17	0.05	0.01	-0.05	0.16	0.01
Leaf angle	G			0.42**	0.55**	0.39**	0.45**	0.15	0.55**	0.06	0.36**
	P			0.30**	0.49**	0.32**	0.32**	0.06**	0.43**	0.06	0.20*
Leaf length	G				0.75**	0.67**	0.89**	-0.29**	0.51**	0.19	0.54**
	P				0.58**	0.58**	0.65**	-0.10	0.36**	0.14	0.31**
Plant height	G					0.73**	0.68**	-0.17	0.57**	0.01	0.63**
	P					0.67**	0.52**	-0.07	0.47**	0.10	0.43**
Panicle length	G						0.57**	-0.16	0.51**	-0.10	0.49**
	P						0.45**	-0.05	0.54**	0.20	0.34**
Sheath length	G							-0.24*	0.53**	0.09	0.43**
	P							-0.26	0.37**	0.06	0.27**
Tillers/plant	G								-0.31**	-0.26**	0.20*
	P								0.22*	-0.19*	0.29**
Grains/panicle	G									0.43**	0.26**
	P									-0.37**	0.36**
Test weight	G										0.27**
	P										0.09

^a Significant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Hot water treatment of rice seed for international shipment

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Hot water treatment to control several seedborne pathogens of rice is a widely used quarantine practice in the international exchange of germplasm. One limitation to its use is potentially

deleterious effects on germination and seedling vigor. The possibility that genotypes may differ substantially in sensitivity to hot water treatment poses serious complications in the interpretation of international testing data.

The effect of different hot water treatments and different posttreatment storage conditions on the seed quality of

four rice cultivars was studied. The cultivars were japonica and indica ecotypes to represent sensitive and resistant responses to hot water treatment. Temperature limits and exposure periods tested encompassed the range of treatment conditions recommended for rice by ASEAN quarantine officials.

Seed quality changes were evaluated